

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: MASSAQUOI
FIRST NAME: JAMES CONRAD
PROGRAM CODE: DIPH
COURSE CODE : ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
 The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:
 The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)
 The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)
 My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%
 The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In research, when researchers collect information....

- They look for specific data to test and support an answer to a question their topic inspired them to ask!¹
- They engage and convince people to provide the information
- They collect and test various data to answer the question they are inspired to ask.
- They do all of the above.

Commented [KG1]: First, you are not consistent with the terminal punctuations. Some options have periods at the end while some do not. If you choose to use terminal punctuations, the footnote superscript should come immediately after the period/punctuation with no space in-between. Kindly review all options to ensure compliance!

2. Which does not fit plagiarism?

- Quoting a source without using quotation marks—even if you do cite it.

Deleted: P

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: 9

Submitting material that, in part or whole, is entirely one's own work but attributing those same portions to their correct source².

the uncredited use (both intentional and unintentional) of somebody else's words or ideas.

Quoting or paraphrasing material without citing the source of that material.

3. Turabian style guide is the student version of the...

The Harvard University Press

The Chicago Manual of Style³

The American Psychological Association

The WHO Rule of Style

4. **If uncertain about which citation styles to use when you do an academic paper**

Use the citation style appropriate to their particular field, once familiar with the style.

Comply with the institution's requirements for academic writing

Use style that is convenient for the writer.

Consult your instructor⁴

5. Reasons for citing your work may not include,

To give credit to the source - researcher/writers.

Commented [KG2]: Rephrase this question to have meaning and punctuate it accordingly!

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 221.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 13.

⁴ Ibid., 141.

Deleted: 4

To show readers that you understand academic writing⁵

To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts.

To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.

6. With a few exceptions, WHO spellings for diseases and other medical terms follow the...

British usage⁶

North American Usage

Both.

None

7. In doing a systematic identification, location and analysis of materials related to the research problem, the researcher does a...

Critical analysis

Literature Review⁷

Summative description

Descriptive analysis

8. When a researcher evaluates the usefulness of sources for relevance, they do the following, except...

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 140.

⁶ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, (World Health Organization, 2013), 13.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 352.

Deleted: .

Deleted: .

Deleted: .

Deleted: .

Formatted: Justified

- Skim page by page in paragraphs in chapters, then the first and last paragraphs that use a lot of keywords
 - Skim its index for your keywords, then skim the pages on which those words occur⁸**
 - Skim the first and last paragraphs in chapters that use a lot of your keywords
 - Skim page by page in paragraphs in chapters that use a lot of your keywords
9. A qualitative research methodology that is based on a descriptive and inductive approach to data collection is
- Critical Incident⁹**
 - Survey.
 - Document Review
 - Online data collection
10. Academic or scholarly writing must produce quality writing that is
- Clear, concise, and explicit
 - Clear, concise, precise, and bold¹⁰**
 - Clear, succinct, precise and to the point
 - Clear, concise, precise and interesting

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 41.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 458.

¹⁰Ibid., 212.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th Ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. Fitzgerald. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Second ed. World Health Organization, 2013.

Deleted: .

Deleted: Volpe,

Deleted: . 2019.

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: .

Deleted: . 2018.

Deleted: . 2013

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.